

Structural study of iron cluster - hetero diene chain S - C - N – C X-ray ORTEP and ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance diagram

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ABSTRACT

Sulphur-iron clusters, like nitrogen-iron clusters, are at the heart of important biochemical movements in cellular life, such as ferredoxin and porphyrin. Knowing the structural nature of this type of clusters is fundamental for the understanding of pathological anomalies of physiological order, understanding the phenomena of chemical signalling, transport and cellular depollution in part. The structural study of the S-C-N-C - iron carbonyl model allows us to understand the nature of the physicochemical interactions of the different atoms of the S-C-N-C chain with the iron atom. After the synthesis of the butadiene-iron carbonyl complex, X-ray PET is studied. IR, SDM and ^1H and ^{13}C NMR analysis is presented. After examination of the spectra, some types of chemical bonds are confirmed

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1. Introduction

The Fe-S cluster lies at the centre of fundamental biochemical activity in the life sciences. Iron-sulphur (Fe/S) centres are small, ancient organometallic protein cofactors found in all living organisms [1 - 4]. The most common centres comprise clusters with two or four iron ions 5 Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of the different types of simple iron–sulfur clusters found in biology. (a) Rubredoxin-like Fe center, (b) [2Fe–2S] cluster, (c) [3Fe–4S] cluster,

Higher cores have been found. They sometimes combine metals different from iron like Cu, Zn or Mn [6]. Their

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role is important in electron transfer reactions [7] Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Schematic representation of the catalytic cycle of cytochrome P450 monooxygenase.

The pathways marked as dotted lines produce oxygen-derived free radicals. In one branch, a superoxide anion is released as a result of the decay of the one-electron-reduced ternary complex (*). The second reactive oxygen species-producing pathway is the protonation of the peroxycytochrome P450. For further details see Davydov [7].

But also, cofactor synthesis, methylation, sulfur insertion and storage, isomerization, etc... [5]. Their biogenesis requires complex protein machineries whose failures in humans are sources of serious pathologies, such as Friedreich's ataxia [8]. Many metalloproteins have active polymetallic sites. In the case of iron, complex arrangements are observed [9]. The interpretation of their behavior requires the study of simple synthetic models. The primary interest of nuclear resonance (the Mössbauer effect), electromagnetic resonance (^{13}C) and the X-ray ORTEP diagram lies in the physical and chemical characterization of these Fe - S centers. This approach allows local information on the centers it affects, in particular on their vibrational state, the local electron density and the various valence and coordination interactions between Iron and its intrinsic surroundings, in particular sulfur, nitrogen, oxygen and carbon atoms known in biology.

The model reported in this paper is a substituted thia -1- Aza -3- butadiene. The complexation method is photochemical in the presence of iron carbonyl $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$.

2. Material and method

The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded using a JEOL FX 90K spectrometer (at 90 MHz for ^1H and 22.115 MHz for ^{13}C). Chemical shifts are expressed in ppm with respect to TMS (Tetra methyl silane) as internal reference. The spectra were performed in CDCl_3 . Abbreviations used: (s) singlet, (d) doublet, (t) triplet, (q) quartet, (m) multiplet, (se) extended singlet.

The infrared spectrum was recorded using an IFS 85 Bruker T.F. Dispersion KBr spectrometer. Mass spectra

recorded using a varian mat 112 dual focus apparatus (Fragmentation energy 70 ev). Purification silica gel Merk Art 1385, Kieselgel 60. The complexation reaction was performed in a photochemical reactor.

Figure 1. X-ray PETRO of Substituted 1-Aza-3-Butadiene
 $C_{13}H_{16}N_2O_2S$: Monoclinique

$$P_{2_1} a = 7,920(4), b = 10,813(3), c = 16,007(4) \text{ \AA}; \beta = 104,88(3)^\circ, Z = 4, m = 9,6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

The study was carried out using an automatic diffractometer CAD 4 ENRAF NONIUS: The parameters of the mesh were determined and refined from a set of 25 high angle reflections. The structure was solved by the Paterson method.

Figure 2. X-Ray PETRA of Carbonyl Iron Substituted 1-Aza-3-Butadiene Complex

$$P_{2_1/c} a = 11,084(4), b = 7,273(4), c = 23,431(7) \text{ \AA}; \beta = 104,88(3)^\circ, Z = 4, m = 9,6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

The study was carried out using an automatic diffractometer CAD 4 ENRAF NONIUS: The parameters of the mesh were determined and refined from a set of 25 high angle reflections. The structure was solved by the Paterson method

3.Results and discussion

Synthesis of substituted thia-1-aza-3-butadiene [10]

a. Thiobenzamide synthesis

b. Synthesis of the orthoamide substituted by a carboxylate

c. Synthesis of substituted thia-1-aza-3-butadiene

d. Photochemical complexation reaction [11].

3.1. Structural studies

3.1.1. Infrared spectroscopy:

The ν (CO) IR frequencies appear in 2059, 1994 and 1975 cm^{-1} .

3.1.2. Mass spectrometry: the presence of the molecular ion depends on the recording conditions of the spectrum. The highest mass fragment ion m/z 376 ($m^+ - CO$) corresponds to the loss of a carbonyl fragment from a molecular ion m/z 404. The successive loss of CO (m/z 28) is characteristic of carbonyl derivatives [12].

3.1.3. X-ray diffraction: The structure of the Mononuclear complex is represented by its X-ray ORTEP [12, 13] Figure: The main interatomic distances and valence angles are reported in Table 1 and 2 .

Table 1. ORTEP X-ray of Substituted 1-Aza-3-Butadiene

Interatomic distances Compound A	
S – C(4)	1,667(5)
C(4) – N(2)	1,335(6)
N(2) – C(3)	1,300(6)
C(3) – N(1)	1,328(7)
Interatomic angles compound B	
S – C(4) – N(2)	124,6(5)
S – C(4) – C(5)	121,7(5)
N(2) – C(4) – C(5)	113,6(4)
N(1) – C(3) – N(2)	120,1(5)

Table 2. ORTEP Iron-substituted thia-1-Aza-3-butadiene X-ray

Interatomic distances Compound B	
S – C(10)	1,742(4)
C(10) – N(1)	1,129(4)
N(1) – C(7)	1,145(4)
C(7) – N(2)	1,452(4)
S - Fe	2,301(2)
C(7) - Fe	2,019 (3)
N(2) - Fe	2,007(3)
Interatomic angles compound B	
S – C(10) – N(1)	122,6(3)
C(10) – N(1) - C(7)	118,1(3)
N(2) – C(7) – C(6)	117,9(3)
Fe – C(7) – N(1)	118,0(2)
S – Fe – C(7)	83,6(0)
S – Fe – N(2)	42,6(0)
S – C(10) C(11)	118,6(3)

Scheme 3. Interatomic distance in Å

The hetero diene chain and the iron atom are coplanar. This flatness contributes to the stability of the metal complex. In compound B the C - N bond is 1.279 Å, similar to an Imine "C = N". On the other hand, the "C - S" bond is longer: 1.742 Å compared to 1.66 Å in compound A. The bond "(CH₃)₂N - Fe" can be explained by the formation of a Dative bond between the free doublet of the nitrogen and the D orbitals of the Iron atom.

3.2. Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy NMR

Table 3. ¹H and ¹³C chemical shifts (ppm / TMS)

	NMR ¹ H	
C ₆ H ₅ -	8,1(m,2H)	8,1(m,2H)
	7,2(m,3H)	7,4(m,3H)
OCH ₂	4,3(q,2H)	4,4(q,2H)
N(CH ₃) ₂	3,1(S,6H)	2,4(s,3H)/ 3,4(s,3H)
NMR ¹³ C		
C - S	112,7	185,6
N - CN	160,6	98,1
CO ester	161,1	169,8
N(CH ₃) ₂	38,6/ 39,2	56,3 /43,7
Fe - CO	---	209,9 206,4

Proton NMR shows that the dimethyl amino - $N(CH_3)_2$ was equivalent in compound A ($\delta = 3.1(S, 6H)$). In compound B the dimethyl amino reveals two peaks: 2.4 (s, 3H), 3.4 (s,3H) which implies the loss of free rotation by engagement of the free nitrogen doublet with the iron atom [14, 11].

4. Conclusion

Modeling the atomic environments of S - Fe and N - Fe clusters is a straightforward approach. It allows the reproduction of clusters chemically by different synthesis strategies. It facilitates the physico-chemical characterization by powerful techniques like XRD, NMR, SDM and IR. Other techniques are also useful: Mössbauer spectroscopy and magnetic susceptibility, electron paramagnetic resonance EPR..., these results will be the subject of a specific communication.

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